

A new species of the genus *Falsomesosella* Pic, 1925 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) from Shaanxi province of China

Новый вид рода *Falsomesosella* Pic, 1925 (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) из Китая, провинция Шэньси

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Abstract. *Falsomesosella taibaishana* Lazarev, **sp.n.**, similar to the Japanese *F. gracilior* (Bates, 1884) and the Taiwanese *F. horishana* Gressitt, 1938, is described from Taibaishan National Park (China, Shaanxi province). It differs from both related species by its pale transverse elytral band curved backwards and dark antennae with joints which are never reddish basally. The distinguishing characters of the new species are discussed.

Резюме. Усач *Falsomesosella taibaishana*, **sp.n.**, близкий к японскому виду *F. gracilior* (Bates, 1884) и тайваньскому *F. horishana* Gressitt, 1938, описан из Национального Парка Тайбайшань (Китай, провинция Шэньси). Он отличается от двух близких видов тёмными антеннами без красноватых оснований члеников и сдвинутой кзади светлой поперечной перевязью надкрылий. Обсуждаются отличительные признаки нового вида.

Introduction

Several long regular expeditions of Russian entomologist Sergey Murzin to China allows him to create an enormous collection of China insects. The most interesting part of that material is represented by Longicorn Beetles (Cerambycidae), which includes many new species. Now is began a regular investigation of his beetles.

Material and Methods

The studied specimens are deposited in the collections of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow) and S.V. Murzin (Moscow).

All photographs were taken with Canon PowerShot G10 digital camera equipped with Cannon Zoom lens 5X IS 6.1 – 30.5 mm 1:2.8–4.5 and microscope AmScope SM745NTP. The illustrations were edited with Adobe Photoshop 7.0 and Helicon Focus 3.20.

Results

Falsomesosella taibaishana Lazarev, **sp.n.**

Figs 1–2.

Material. *Holotype* (male): China, Shaanxi province, Taibaishan National Park, 1350 m, 10.06.1999, S. Murzin leg. — collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow). **Paratypes:** 1 male, 2 females, with same label — collections of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow) and S.V. Murzin (Moscow).

Description. Body totally black including antennae and legs; head densely covered with brown recumbent pubescence; genae about as long as lower eye lobe; lower eye lobe connected with upper lobe by very narrow bridge, not totally separated; antennal tubercles rounded with deep depression in between, divided by the width of apical portion of 1st antennal joint; antenna much longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 5 distal joints, with moderately long ciliae shortened distally; all joints rather dark, nearly black, with white basal setae rings; 1st antennal joint rather wide with thick and long lateral apical process; 1st joint a little shorter than 4th and much shorter than 3rd; 3rd joint with numerous small spots of pale setae, which are more or less distinct on other joints.

Prothorax transverse, about 1.2 times shorter than basal width in males, and about 1.25 in females, slightly regularly widened at sides, without lateral tubercles; pronotum irregularly convex, with a pair of hardly pronounced central elevations, with small dense irregular punctation, which can be scattered along middle; covered by sported brownish pubescence.

Scutellum small, roundish, with dark pubescence. Elytra about 2 times longer than wide in males and in females, widened behind middle, rounded or truncated apically; with very small humeral convexities and small depression before middle, with small dense punctation, covered by irregular brownish pubescence with scattered pale setae, with wide pale transverse band at middle, slightly moved backwards, bearing several dark spots; pale band always strongly reduced near suture; sometimes it is distinct near lateral elytral margins only; several small areas of pale setae could be visible near elytral apices; legs with scattered pale pubescence;

Figs 1–3. *Falsomesosella* spp. 1–2: *Falsomesosella taibaishana*, sp.n. 1 — male, holotype, dorsal view, 2 — female, paratype, dorsal view. 3 — *F. horishana*, holotype, male, Taiwan, Hori (Horisha, Polisia); photo by L. G. Bezark [<http://bezbycids.com>].

Рис. 1–3. *Falsomesosella* spp. 1–2: *Falsomesosella taibaishana*, sp.n. 1 — самец, голотип, вид сверху, 2 — самка, паратип, вид сверху. 3 — *F. horishana*, 1938, голотип, самец, Тайвань (Хориша, Полисия); фотография сделана Л.Г. Безарком [<http://bezbycids.com>].

1st joint of posterior tarsi about as long as 2nd and 3rd combined.

Abdomen with moderately long, dense pale pubescence; last abdominal sternite in males rounded apically, as well as pygidium and postpygidium; last abdominal sternite in females strongly convex, with deep central furrow and sparser pubescence, slightly emarginated apically; last abdominal tergite in females also slightly emarginated apically.

Body length in males: 8.1–9.2 mm, width: 2.7–2.9 mm, body length in females: 9.2–11.0 mm, width: 3.1–3.6 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The new species is close to Japanese *F. gracilior* (Bates, 1884), but *F. gracilior* is usually smaller (6–11 mm), pronotum partly shining, with less developed punctation; pale elytral band much more distinct, with less number of dark dots; not reduced near middle. *F. gracilior* was often depicted by Japanese authors [Kojima, Hayashi, 1969; Hayashi et al., 1984; Kusama, Takakuwa, 1984; Makihara, 2007].

Another closely related species is Taiwanese *F. horishana* W.Gressitt, 1938 (Fig. 3), but that one has parallelsided elytra. Besides both related species have reddish antennae, and pale transverse elytral band moved anteriorly before elytral middle.

Distribution. The new species is only known from the type locality in Taibaishan National Park (Taibaishan Mountain Range, Shaanxi Province of China).

Etymology. The species is named after the name of the type locality — Taibaishan Mountain Range.

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